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FTP-3**An Analytic Evaluation of Material, Pressure, Cutting Speed, and Water Jet Diameter's Effect on the Surface Quality for the Water Jet Cutting**

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The Abrasive Water Jet (AWJ) cutting process uses abrasive particles in a highly pressurized water jet for cutting the metallic and non-metallic materials. It has more advantageous features compared to other cutting methods. AWJ can eliminate toxic gases, recast layers, slag, and thermal stresses. In this study, the result of the AWJ cutting experiments will be presented. The experiments were performed on two types of steel materials which are widely used in the aviation and naval industry. These materials are BS 7191 355 EMZ and ASTM A516 Gr.60 plates of steel. In total, 180 cuttings were performed with pre-assigned water jet pressure, speed, and diameter parameters. At the end of the experimental study, it was determined that; between both steels; BS 7191 355 EMZ provides a comparatively higher surface quality than ASTM A516 Gr.60 using a small water jet diameter, low rate speed, and low pressure.

Keywords: Abrasive Water Jet, Surface Quality, Material Type, Pressure, Cutting Speed, Water Jet Diameter

Author's Note: This study is based on the author's doctoral dissertation that is titled “Analysis of Material, Pressure, Cutting Velocity and Water Jet Diameter’s Effect on the Surface Quality for the Water Jet Cutting” under the supervision of Prof. Dr. Yaşar Pancar.

1. Introduction

The usage of pressurized water in the industry started in the second half of the 1800s. It was used to extract soft gold stones from mining surfaces. However, as a cutting process usage of the water jet cutting started in Russia in the 1930s. In the 1960s, Exotech Terraspace Company developed the high-pressure pumps that might the possibility of using in the water jet machines. In the first stage of the 1970s, with the usage of high-pressure pumps first, commercial applications started in wood pipe cutting in water jet operations. In the 1980s, by adding abrasive particles to the water jet, the abrasive water jet manufacturing method has been put into practice. Since the beginning of the 2000s with the usage of high-pressure intensifiers in the AWJ machines, the AWJ applications have taken place in the industry more widely.

In time AWJ has gained more popularity in different industries such as aerospace, aviation, medical, and so on. It is well-known that the competition in the aviation industry is fierce. This challenging competition always requires implementation of the novel technologies sometimes unless they are not matured satisfactorily. Aviation has been compelled to be a leader in the adoption of revolutionary manufacturing techniques like Computer-Aided Design (CAD), Computer-Aided Manufacturing (CAM), and newly created materials like carbon

fiber composites. The aviation sector was the first to utilize these technologies and materials. After the aviation industry adopted several techniques and materials as standard, other industries such as automotive, shipbuilding, and white goods adopted them [1].

Many disruptive innovation examples brought the incidents just after implementation. These novel implementations carry the potential flight-safety risks when they are impetuous as happened in Boeing 737 Max accidents. On October 29, 2018, and on March 10, 2019, two Boeing 737-Max commercial passengers crashed and 346 people lost their lives [2]. The International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO), which is part of the United Nations (UN), is also one of the UN's largest and most successful agencies. ICAO, as a top organization in the aviation industry, put the rules that should be obeyed in terms of flight and ground safety. Manufacturers, maintenance organizations, and users of aircraft, engines, and other components must comply with these rules as an obligation [3, 4, 5]. ICAO, on the other hand, warns in its global aviation safety plan 2020-2022 that new technology and concepts may have a negative influence on flight safety if they are not fully matured [6]. Meaningfully a matured process provides more safe solutions in terms of flight safety. In this regard, it should be underlined that the AWJ process has been used in

the aviation industry for a very long time. It can be considered a mature technology.

It is accepted as much as legacy manufacturing technologies by aircraft part manufacturers. For example, Boeing Company which is one of the world's largest airplane manufacturers has made the 5-axis AWJ machine a standard machine because it prevents delamination, splitting, and edge scratches during the cutting process [7]. In addition, AWJ is considered the most suitable cutting method in the process of shaping the parts up to the part boundary (EOP- End of Product) [8].

In the open literature, there are many studies regarding AWJ. Natarajan and his friends made large literature research and submitted a review study [9]. They underlined the studies in aerospace regarding the drilling of precise micro-holes on the structural parts. In this study, some applications in the automobile, medical, cutting tools, and process development were also provided. In another study, Fermin Bañon and his friends investigated the AWJ cutting of metal-carbon fiber hybrid materials [10]. After a detailed explanation of the AWJ machine working principle, they underlined the taper and taper defect of the kerf structure. The surface quality in the AWJ of Polymeric Matrix Composites (PMC) was inspected in this study. They claimed that the AWJ process provides sufficient efficiency in cutting hybrid materials. For Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) materials cut with the AWJ machine, Demiral and friends made an experimental study in terms of delamination [11]. They mainly focused on the CFRP cross-ply delamination under different cutting parameters. In this study, it was claimed that; different failure behaviors such as fiber pull-out, fiber breaking, fiber debonding, matrix cracking, and delamination are observed when particle pressure and impact angle are varied.

For stainless steel materials, Supriya and Srinivas made a study on AWJ machinability [12]. In this study, the efficiency of AWJ was underlined when compared to conventional cutting processes for stainless steel materials. Other than the hybrid, CFRP, and some stainless steel, other metallic materials such as titanium cutting were also investigated by the researchers. Percec made experimental research for AWJ cutting of titanium material [13]. During the cutting process, he changed the abrasive materials as GMA80 (Garnet), Glass125 and olivine respectively. At the end of his study, Percec found that the garnet abrasive material provides the greatest cutting depth while olivine and crushed glass particles provide lower cutting depth. It was also underlined that the AWJ can be used to

machine any material without affecting the surface structure or qualities.

In another study prepared by Saraçyakupoğlu under the supervision of Prof. Dr. Yaşar Pancar, the correlation between surface quality and cutting parameters for BS 7191 355 EMZ and ASTM A516 Gr.60 steels using AWJ was investigated as a doctoral dissertation [14]. They made 180 cuttings with two types of mentioned steels with a variety of pressure, cutting speed, and water jet diameter in terms of having the high surface quality. At the end of the experimental study, it was claimed that; BS 7191 355 EMZ steel provides a higher surface quality compared to ASTM A516 Gr.60.

2. Materials and Methods

AWJ machines are comparatively complex machines. It's a versatile method that can achieve great productivity through high material removal rates. It also produces modest machining forces and, more importantly, a fairly limited temperature range as compared to traditional techniques.

2.1. The General Information about the AWJ Working Principle

AWJ machining involves the rapid acceleration of a mixture of fluid and solid particles, which causes deformation or removal of the target material as illustrated in Figure 1.a. and the part being processed by the AWJ machine.

The jet can be made with any liquid, although most are made of a mixture of water and air for cost and environmental reasons. Because water has a higher density, it exerts more impact pressure during machining. In the mixing chamber, the pressurized water and abrasive particles mix with the force of suction created by high pressure. Mainly this flow-mechanism is called as "jet-pump" [15].

In this relatively narrow mixing chamber, the momentum of the highly pressurized water transfers to abrasive particles and reaches the capability of a wide variety of materials precisely. At present, the average pressure of an AWJ machine is between 3000-4000 bar. Mainly garnets are used as abrasive materials. Dr. M. Hashish developed a method for adding abrasives to a regular waterjet in 1979. Garnet of mesh size 80 is often utilized as an abrasive particle in AWJ machines after testing a variety of possibilities. Dr. M. Hashish focused on the usage of AWJ in the aviation industry and performed many experiments that enlightened the weight and balance optimizations [16]. In some cases, it has been observed that aluminum oxide and olivine are also used.

Figure 1.a. The Illustration of AWJ Water and Abrasives Mixing Mechanism; 1.b. The Workpiece Being Cut

It is noteworthy that AWJM is used for pocket milling, drilling, peening, and other operations in addition to cutting. Abrasive water jet machining (AWJM) has been developed as a hybrid machining technology for polishing and cleaning with a high-pressure abrasive water jet to get a superior surface finish.

Aside from cutting, AWJ machining is utilized for operations such as pocket milling, drilling, and peening. In order to achieve a better surface quality, research and development on AWJ machining have been conducted to use procedure as a hybrid machining method for polishing and cleaning with high-pressure abrasive water jet [17].

In an AWJ Process temperature is not as much of a factor so Heat Affected Zone (HAZ) may not be an impacting phenomenon. It is an overwhelming feature that increases the importance of AWJ usage. However, the noisy operation is one of the constraints of the AWJ.

2.2. The Cutting Experiments

In this study, an optimized parameter-set of cutting was targeted. In this manner, 180 cuttings were performed for two different kinds of steels that are broadly used in the aviation and naval industry as it was mentioned before. The total thickness of the coupons is selected as 400 mm which is an average thickness for the machine. Before cutting, process etching was applied to all coupons for the surface preparation. The machine was set up for the cutting operations using alternated values for water jet diameter, cutting speed and pressure for BS 7191 355 EMZ and ASTM A516 Gr.60 steels. The parameters were selected as follows.

- Water Jet Diameter: 1, “1,1”, “1,2”, “1,3”, “1,4”, “1,5” (mm)
- Cutting Speed: 20, 25, 30 (mm/min)
- Pressure: 3300, 3350, 3400, 3450, 3500 (bar)

With the above-given parameters, the table provided in Table 1. was prepared. 180 test coupons were cut using the parameters provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Test Cut Parameters Selected for the Experiments for Each Steel Type

# Cut	Water Jet Diameter (mm)	Cutting Speed (mm/min)	Pressur e (Bar)	# Cu t	Water Jet Diameter (mm)	Cutting Speed (mm/min)	Pressur e (Bar)	# Cu t	Water Jet Diameter (mm)	Cutting Speed (mm/min)	Pressur e (Bar)
1	1	20	3300	31	1,2	20	3300	61	1,4	20	3300
2	1	25	3300	32	1,2	25	3300	62	1,4	25	3300
3	1	30	3300	33	1,2	30	3300	63	1,4	30	3300
4	1	20	3350	34	1,2	20	3350	64	1,4	20	3350
5	1	25	3350	35	1,2	25	3350	65	1,4	25	3350
6	1	30	3350	36	1,2	30	3350	66	1,4	30	3350
7	1	20	3400	37	1,2	20	3400	67	1,4	20	3400
8	1	25	3400	38	1,2	25	3400	68	1,4	25	3400
9	1	30	3400	39	1,2	30	3400	69	1,4	30	3400
10	1	20	3450	40	1,2	20	3450	70	1,4	20	3450
11	1	25	3450	41	1,2	25	3450	71	1,4	25	3450
12	1	30	3450	42	1,2	30	3450	72	1,4	30	3450
13	1	20	3500	43	1,2	20	3500	73	1,4	20	3500
14	1	25	3500	44	1,2	25	3500	74	1,4	25	3500
15	1	30	3500	45	1,2	30	3500	75	1,4	30	3500
16	1,1	20	3300	46	1,3	20	3300	76	1,5	20	3300
17	1,1	25	3300	47	1,3	25	3300	77	1,5	25	3300
18	1,1	30	3300	48	1,3	30	3300	78	1,5	30	3300
19	1,1	20	3350	49	1,3	20	3350	79	1,5	20	3350
20	1,1	25	3350	50	1,3	25	3350	80	1,5	25	3350
21	1,1	30	3350	51	1,3	30	3350	81	1,5	30	3350
22	1,1	20	3400	52	1,3	20	3400	82	1,5	20	3400
23	1,1	25	3400	53	1,3	25	3400	83	1,5	25	3400
24	1,1	30	3400	54	1,3	30	3400	84	1,5	30	3400
25	1,1	20	3450	55	1,3	20	3450	85	1,5	20	3450
26	1,1	25	3450	56	1,3	25	3450	86	1,5	25	3450
27	1,1	30	3450	57	1,3	30	3450	87	1,5	30	3450
28	1,1	20	3500	58	1,3	20	3500	88	1,5	20	3500
29	1,1	25	3500	59	1,3	25	3500	89	1,5	25	3500
30	1,1	30	3500	60	1,3	30	3500	90	1,5	30	3500

2.3. Mechanical Properties of ASTM A516 Grade 60 and BS 7191 355 EMZ Steels

The link between a material's response to or deformation from an applied load or force is reflected in its mechanical characteristics. In other words, the materials' working condition is directly related to the mechanical features. When it comes to

steel, the mechanical characteristics of the steel grade can frequently imply the difference between frequent or even catastrophic failure in the most abrasive and wear-intensive applications. In Table 2. Yield, tensile, elongation, and hardness information are provided comparatively.

Table 2. The Mechanical Properties Comparison of ASTM A516 Grade 60 and BS 7191 355 EMZ Steels [18, 19, 20]

The Mechanical Properties of ASTM A516 Grade 60 and BS 7191 355 EMZ Steels	Yield	Tensile	Elongation	Brinell Hardness (HBW)
	Rp0.2 (MPa)	Rm (MPa)	A (%)	
BS 7191 355 EMZ	556 (≥)	269 (≥)	34	241
ASTM A516 Grade 60	415-550	220 (≥)	24	211

2.4. Chemical Composition of the Chemical Compositions of ASTM A516 Grade 60 and BS 7191 355 EMZ Steels

As it was mentioned before both ASTM A516 Grade 60 and BS 7191 355 EMZ steels are commonly used

in the naval and aviation industry. These two materials are preferred by the manufacturers on the water-touch surfaces of the vessel and seaplanes. The chemical compositions of the steels are provided in Table 3.

Table 3. Chemical Compositions of ASTM A516 Grade 60 and BS 7191 355 EMZ Steels [18, 19, 20]

Chemical Compositions of ASTM A516 Grade 60 and BS 7191 355 EMZ Steels					
ASTM A516 Grade 60 Chemical Composition			BS 7191 355 EMZ Chemical Composition		
Element	Min	Max	Element	Min	Max
C		0.18	C	-	0.15
Si		0.4	Si	0.25	0.55
Mn	0,95	1,5	Mn	1	1.65
P		0.015	P	-	0.025
S		0.008	S	-	0.008
Al	0.02	-	Al	-	0.055
Cu		0.3	Cu	-	0.3
Ni		0.3	Ni	-	0.45
Mo		0.08	Mo	-	0.08
Nb		0.01	Nb	-	0.04
Ti		0.03	Ti	-	0.02
V		0.02	V	-	0.015
Cr		0.3	Cr	-	0.25
			Sn	-	0.015
			Sb	-	0.01
			V+Nb	-	0.1

3. Results

After 180 cuts were performed per parameters given in the Table 1., the surface roughnesses were inspected. For analyzing the cut surface roughness,

an area 5 mm. below the top surface was selected. In Figure 2.a. the kerf geometry, in Figure 2.b. inspected areas of processed coupons, and in Figure 2.c. an evaluated result is shown.

Figure 2.a. The Kerf Geometry, 2.b. Inspected Areas of Cut Coupon, 2.c. An evaluated Result

The kerf geometry can be calculated from the Formula (1).

$$\text{Kerf taper} = (W_t - W_b) / 2t \tag{1}$$

For every assigned parameter set of each cutting, a surface measurement was done for the evaluation of

the surface roughness. The evaluation is shown for the cutting operation given in Figure 5.

Consequently, for 180 cutting operations, all data was collected for BS 7191 355 EMZ, and ASTM A516 Gr.60 steels as provided in Table 4.

Table 4. The Surface Roughness Values of ASTM A516 Grade 60 and BS 7191 355 EMZ Steels

# Cut	Surface Roughness (Å) BS 7191 355 EMZ	Surface Roughness (Å) ASTM A516 Gr.60	# Cut	Surface Roughness (Å) BS 7191 355 EMZ	Surface Roughness (Å) ASTM A516 Gr.60	# Cut	Surface Roughness (Å) BS 7191 355 EMZ	Surface Roughness (Å) ASTM A516 Gr.60
1	25201	30930	31	30827	33139	61	33036	35348
2	26452	31193	32	31094	33402	62	34317	36617
3	28415	31450	33	31364	33666	63	34587	36883
4	28735	31504	34	31429	33719	64	34632	36932
5	28935	31542	35	31440	33750	65	34654	36963
6	29062	31585	36	31488	33790	66	34693	37004
7	29240	31622	37	31520	33831	67	34727	37038
8	29610	32315	38	32218	34527	68	34927	37235
9	29946	32400	39	32401	34611	69	35134	37446
10	30178	33082	40	32995	35296	70	35211	37521
11	30358	33342	41	33275	35551	71	35469	37779
12	30698	33602	42	33504	35816	72	35612	38931
13	30974	33867	43	33765	36077	73	36127	39294
14	31037	34453	44	34356	36666	74	36368	39880
15	31055	35075	45	34987	37289	75	36927	41444
16	29721	32033	46	31953	34245	76	33567	39496
17	29998	32299	47	32209	34509	77	33604	40577
18	30267	32559	48	32365	34777	78	33638	41612
19	30296	32611	49	32515	34825	79	33791	41899
20	30342	32644	50	32547	34855	80	33980	42258
21	30377	32689	51	32588	34898	81	34126	42417
22	30424	32726	52	32621	34932	82	34426	42685
23	31110	33421	53	33323	35633	83	36728	44244
24	31182	33504	54	33410	35718	84	38484	46098
25	31897	34189	55	34098	36400	85	38677	46278
26	32154	34446	56	34347	36657	86	38844	46399
27	32497	34709	57	34531	36823	87	38935	46681
28	32862	34974	58	34873	37185	88	39099	46820
29	33247	35559	59	35466	37773	89	39677	47453
30	33669	36181	60	36088	38395	90	40964	48217

The surface roughness comparison of BS 7191 355 EMZ and ASTM A516 Gr.60 is shown in Figure 3. It can be seen that both materials' surface quality is close to each other.

Figure 3. The Surface Roughness Comparison of BS 7191 355 EMZ and ASTM A516 Gr.60 Steels

4. Conclusion

In this work, the BS 7191 355 EMZ and ASTM A516 Gr.60 steels were subjected to AWJ cutting with alternated, pressure, cutting speed, and jet diameter parameters. To be more precise, the surface machining markings may develop into stress concentrators, which can quicken component crack nucleation. That's why the surface quality has a vital importance for the aviation-grade material processing.

During experiments two materials were compared to each other. After 180 cuts were performed.

Results of the present work indicate that BS 7191 355 EMZ steel leads to a higher surface finish when compared to ASTM A516 Gr.60.

Conclusionally, it was found that; under the same circumstances the following features provides a higher surface quality.

Material : BS 7191 355 EMZ.
Pressure : 3300 bar
Cutting Speed : 20 mm/min
Water Jet (Nozzle Diameter) : 1 mm

Besides, for the same materials, the higher surface quality is gained as the pressure, cutting speed and water jet diameter are decreased. For future studies, producing more samples with different parameters changing the cutting pressure, and performing mechanical tests are recommended.

5. Acknowledge

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